

DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION COMPETENCY IN FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: The role of physical culture in the development of professional competence of future physical education teachers is incomparable. This thesis talks about the role and importance of physical culture in the development of professional competence of future physical education teachers.

Key words: physical culture, education, normative, transformative, cognitive, value-oriented, communicative, professional competence, practical lexicon.

Introduction.

Establishing a healthy way of life in our country, creating conditions for the population, especially the young generation, to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports, strengthening the confidence of young people in their will, strength and capabilities through sports competitions, courage and patriotism, developing feelings of loyalty to the Motherland, as well as systematic organization of selection of talented athletes from among young people, and large-scale work aimed at further development of physical education is being carried out.

When studying issues related to the scientific pedagogical activity of future physical education teachers, it is appropriate to analyze the essence of the concepts related to this phenomenon. In the modern world, the role of physical culture as a factor in improving the nature of man and society is increasing significantly. Today, the future physical education teacher is always engaged in his education and training in parallel with delivering physical exercises to students, and interacts with him. In the pedagogical activities of the future physical education teacher, the most important components are to be devoted to the teaching profession, to have a perfect knowledge of the methodology of teaching one's subject, to be able to demonstrate pedagogical skills, and to be able to use pedagogical techniques in their place. is considered to be

Speaking about the role of physical culture in the development of professional competence of future physical education teachers, it is appropriate to first look at the history of this concept. The term "physical culture" itself

appeared in England at the end of the 19th century during the rapid development of sports, but was not widely used in the West and over time almost disappeared from everyday life. In Russia, on the contrary, from the beginning of the 20th century, after the revolution of 1917, the term "physical culture" began to be recognized by all high Soviet authorities and firmly entered the scientific and practical lexicon. The importance of physical education and sports in the development of professional competence of future physical education teachers and their introduction into everyday life is increasing. Physical education and sports prepare a person for life, exercise his body and strengthen his health, contribute to his well-rounded physical development, personal skills necessary in professional work to develop the professional competence of future physical education teachers of the national economy. helps to educate virtues, moral and physical qualities.

Modern ideas about physical culture in the development of professional competence of future physical education teachers are related to evaluating it as a unique part of general culture. Improving the physical culture of future physical education teachers means a set of human characteristics acquired in the process of physical exercises and expressed in an active effort to improve a person's physical nature (physicality) comprehensively and harmoniously, to lead a healthy lifestyle. He actively develops initiative, independence and creativity, forms his worldview and ways of thinking, individual character traits, critical attitude to other people's actions and his own actions.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, all these positive characteristics obtained as a result of physical culture in the development of professional competence of future physical education teachers make a person not only a physically cultured person, but also a well-rounded and well-developed person, reflecting a high level of general culture of the person. is described.

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